

THE MAIN CRITERIA OF GENDER LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. In present level gender linguistics is appeared as one of developing direction to learn language more deeply and to analyze the reflection of gender in it. The study of men and women representation accesses us to identify language mechanisms that express gender relations and realize the matter happening in language and society.

Phraseology represents as retranslation of culture and appears as successful source to research the relations between genders. This system includes stereotypical behavior and perception of men and women for representators of opposite genders.

Key words gender, gender linguistics, biological determenism, sociolinguistic, grammatical category, noun class

Introduction

The increasing interest towards the individual characteristics of personality means that in the nearest future the problems of gender and language interrelations will no longer be discrete and fragmentary. The process of a separate scientific formation – linguistic genderology, is taking place in modern linguistics.

The problem of gender researches in linguistics can be viewed both diachronically and synchronically and they are closely interrelated. The study of gender and language interrelation is usually divided into two periods . The first period is called the period of biological determinism, which means occasional researches with no connection to related sciences and based on the observation of discrete facts. The second period includes gender researches themselves. Those are large-scale researches that have been conducted since the 1960s due to increasing interest towards the pragmatic aspect of linguistics, the development of In present level gender linguistics is appeared as one of developing direction to learn language more deeply and to analyze the reflection of gender in it. The study of men and women representation accesses us to identify language mechanisms that express gender relations and realize the matter happening in language and society.

Phraseology represents as retranslation of culture and appears as successful source to research the relations between genders. This system includes stereotypical behavior and perception of men and women for representators of opposite genders and considerable changes in traditional distribution of male and female roles in the society. All these factors helped the scientists consider the linguistic facts as well as interpret them in a new way.

A great number of researches of Ukrainian and foreign linguists are dedicated to the problems of gender linguistics as well as to the usage of gender marked lexis in different languages. The works and researches of T.B. Kryutchkova, M. Fuko, A.A. Veylert, E.I. Goroshko, L.R. Moshinskaya, O.A. Ryuzakina, E.A. Zemskaya, T.V. Gomon, Pershai A. Yu, Kirilina A.V and others made an invaluable contribution into the development of the general theory of gender linguistics, in particular into the problem of interrelation of psychology and linguistics.

The notion “gender” came in modern linguistic paradigm later than the other sciences. First this notion was used as the grammatical category of a noun. From the history of English language we may observe that people used to name things according to their feature or who from them female or male used these things.

Grammatical gender is defined linguistically as classes of nouns which trigger specific types of behavior in associated words, such as adjectives, verbs and others. Genders are types of noun classes in which the gender is referenced by the structure of the word. Every noun must belong to one of the classes and there should be very few that belong to several classes at once. If a language distinguishes between genders, each noun in that language will belong to one of those genders: in order to correctly decline any noun and any modifier or other type of word affecting that noun, one must identify the gender of the subject. While Old English (Anglo-Saxon) had grammatical gender, Modern English is normally described as lacking grammatical gender.

The linguistic notion of grammatical gender is distinguished from the biological and social notion of natural gender, although they interact closely in many languages. Both grammatical and natural gender can have linguistic effects in a given language. Although some authors use the term "noun class" as a synonym or an extension of "grammatical gender", for others they are separate concepts. One can in fact say that grammatical gender is a type of noun class, as well as a grammatical category.

Many scientists connect this notion with the ancient times. In their opinion the gender of words relates to the Gods. The word love was feminine because the God of love Aphrodite was female. Athena was the goddess of wisdom. That's why, the word wisdom also considered be feminine. Hestia , was the goddess of the hearth (fireplace, traditional center of the family, home). So the words family also was considered to be feminine. On the opposite, the words with hard character were masculine gender. Zeus was the chief of the gods. His domain was the sky. Hephaestus was the god of fire. Hercules proved his courage and strength by completing twelve very difficult tasks. Many idioms created with the name of Gods and heroes in myths.

For example, from myth the phraseological unit “a Herculean labour or task” appeared and meant a very difficult duty or task. Personification let us substitute the following nouns to personal pronouns “he” or “she”.

Presently the horse came to him on Monday morning, with a saddle on his back and a bit in his mouth, and said, Camel , O Camel, come out and trot like rest of us. (R. Kipling)

The words: boat, ship, steamer, vessel, car, train, earth, moon, church, nature, soul, night, liberty, mercy, country, England belong to feminine and may be substituted by the pronoun “she”.

Sun, time, ocean, love, anger, discord, murder, river may be substituted by the pronoun “he”.

In the following sonnet of Shakespeare we may find case of gender,

*When forty winters shall besiege thy brow,
And dig deep trenches in thy beauty's field,
Thy youth's proud livery, so gaz'd on now,
Will be a tatter'd weed, of small worth held:
Then being ask'd where all thy beauty lies,
Where all the treasure of thy lusty days;
To say, within thine own deep sunken eyes,
Were on all eating shame and thriftless praise .
How much more praise deserv'd thy beauty's use,
If thou couldst answer – This fair child of mine,
Shall Sum my count , and make my old excuse,
Proving his beauty by succession thine!*

*This were to be new made when thou art old,
And see thy blood warm when thou feel'st it cold.*

Here we may observe that at that time the feature of gender peculiarities in phraseological units and pronouns appeared in the language. Many languages kept the old tradition of gender case of nouns. For this reason it is easier to observe gender peculiarities of nouns and phrases.

They are kept especially in the languages which have articles which denote gender in use. But in modern English the feature of gender peculiarities clearly observed in pronouns. *For example*, the personal pronoun “he” or objective pronoun “him” is masculine and the personal pronoun “she” or objective pronoun “her” is feminine. The gender peculiarities are also observed in names of professions. Like actor is masculine and actress is feminine words. But the researches showed that not all names of professions can be considered to one gender.

For example, the name of profession “doctor” is used with both gender members. In some books the gender of such name of professions is given with the definition of gender member, woman doctor or man doctor and etc.

It is not unimportant that a person uses 'chick' nor unimportant that he stops using it. Every act reproduces or subverts a social institution (in the above case, relations between men and women) Trevor Pateman, Language, Truth and Politics (1975)

Conclusion

Gender in speech is appeared with the position of men and women in a society. It is very changeable notion because the position of man and woman are getting more different than it was before. So the words and their usage are changing every day. Some words or phrases which were used only for man nowadays are used for both gender members. This theme interested many scientists especially the members of the language that has gender features like German, Russian and French.

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